

**DEDICATED TO ANALYSIS OF THE ESSENCE OF DOCUMENTS
CONFIRMING THE AUTHORIZATION OF LAWYERS IN UZBEKISTAN
THESIS**

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ABSTRACT

In a democratic state governed by the rule of law and a fair civil society, the lawyer plays an important role. The Bar is a democratic legal institution that ensures the constitutional right of every person to receive qualified legal assistance on a professional basis. Thus, according to Article 116 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the right to qualified legal assistance is guaranteed at any stage of the investigation and trial. The Bar provides legal assistance to citizens, enterprises, institutions and organizations. The organization of the legal profession and the procedure for its work are determined by law. The warrant confirms that the lawyer is authorized to handle a particular case. However, according to the legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in some cases one warrant is not enough.

Article 61 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan (IPC) provides that, naturally, only lawyers can engage in professional activities in presenting cases in court. However, it should be recognized that today there are controversial cases of the participation of a lawyer in the conduct of business affairs, and we considered it necessary to talk about this in the article.

For example, during a court hearing, in a number of cases, lawyers present only a lawyer's power of attorney as a document confirming that they have procedural authority to participate in the court hearing, and report that all rights and powers are granted by a lawyer's power of attorney

In fact, in Article 49 of the Code of Criminal Procedure, a defense attorney is a person who has the authority to protect the rights and legitimate interests of suspects, defendants, defendants in accordance with the law and provide them with the necessary legal assistance, lawyers may participate in the case as defense attorneys, participation of a lawyer in a case is allowed after he presents his lawyer's license and submits a power of attorney confirming his authority to conduct a specific case, which allows lawyers to effectively protect the rights and interests of citizens by simplifying the mechanism of participation as a defense attorney at any stage of the criminal process, protects the protected person from

various forms harassment and pressure. From the above it is clear that, unlike criminal procedural legislation, economic procedural legislation does not provide for the mandatory participation of a lawyer in the consideration of the economic court and is based on the discretion and will of the parties.

In accordance with Article 61 of the Economic Procedural Code, only lawyers can engage in the professional activity of representing cases in court.

In particular, Article 62 of the IPC notes that the powers of a representative (lawyers to act in court must be indicated in a power of attorney issued and executed in accordance with the law. For example, during economic proceedings, when a plaintiff is presented with a petition signed by a lawyer to waive the claim for collection of the amount owed to the defendant, the court first of all checks for the presence of a power of attorney to waive his claim whether the requirement is specifically provided for in the power of attorney or not. If the attorney is given such authority in the power of attorney, the application is considered to have been filed by the attorney, and if this authority is not granted, the application will be rejected.

As well as Article 63 of the Economic Procedural Code provides that such powers as signing a statement of claim, transferring a case to an arbitration court, partial or complete waiver of claims and recognition of a claim, changing the subject or basis of a claim, concluding a settlement agreement, an agreement on mediation. procedure or mediation agreement, transfer of powers to another person (assignment), appeal of a court document, signing an application for re-examination of a court document that has entered into legal force (with the exception of the requirement for the forced execution of a court document, obtaining recovery of property or money) must be specifically provided for in the power of attorney.

In addition, Article 62 of the Economic Procedural Code provides that a person acting as a representative under a contract (except for a lawyer), in addition to a power of attorney, is required to submit to the court a document confirming the status of the representative under the contract.

In this case, it is determined that a lawyer, when performing the functions of a representative under a contract, is not required to submit an agreement (contract) for the provision of legal assistance, but the question arises about the need to submit a power of attorney for the participation of a lawyer remains open for now.

According to decision No. 13 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2019 “On some issues of application of norms of economic procedural law by the court of first instance,” a warrant issued by a Legal Consultation or Bar Association (bureau, firm) of a person who has applied to a lawyer for legal assistance gives the right to protect one’s interests, but does not replace a power of attorney and does not give the lawyer the right to perform procedural actions specifically provided for in Article 63 of the Economic Procedural Code.

In practice, this norm of the Plenum decision itself is interpreted in two ways. In particular, the courts require the presence of a power of attorney in addition to the power of attorney, citing the fact that the power of attorney gives the lawyer the right to protect the interests of the person seeking legal assistance, but does not replace the power of attorney. Lawyers emphasize that a power of attorney is needed only for carrying out procedural actions provided for in Article 63 of the Economic Procedural Code .

Thus, participants in economic proceedings have different approaches to the issue of the participation of a lawyer in economic proceedings.

Here, according to Article 4 of the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On guarantees of advocacy and social protection of lawyers,” the order confirms that the lawyer is authorized to conduct a certain case.

According to Article 7 of this law, it is prohibited to require any special permission (except for power of attorney and power of attorney) or create other obstacles in the exercise of legal practice.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to note paragraph five of paragraph 14 of decision No. 13 of the Plenum of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 24, 2019 “On some issues of application of the norms of legislation of the Republic of Uzbekistan.” economic procedural law by the court of first instance" as follows:

“A power of attorney issued by a legal consultation or a bar association (bureau, firm) gives the lawyer the right to protect the interests of a person who has applied for legal assistance. However, to carry out procedural actions specifically provided for in Article 63 of the IPC, a properly executed power of attorney is required”.

We believe that the presentation of this paragraph in the proposed wording in the decision of the Plenum will create additional grounds for legal entities and individuals to receive qualified legal assistance, eliminating controversial situations in the process of determining the powers of a lawyer in litigation.

In conclusion, we can say that the request by a commercial court of a power of attorney from a lawyer should be understood not as a violation of the freedom of advocacy or obstruction of this activity, but as a clear definition of the powers to act in court and to ensure the possibility of effective use of procedural powers in court proceedings.

List of used literature:

1. Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan <http://lex.uz//docs/-6445145>
2. UzR. Law “On Advocacy”. <http://lex.uz//ru/docs/-54503>
3. UzR. Law “On guarantees of the legal profession and social protection of lawyers.” <http://lex.uz//docs/-29626>
4. Civil Procedure Code <http://lex.uz//docs/-3517337>
5. Code of economic procedure <http://lex.uz//ru/docs/-3523891>
6. Criminal Procedure Code <http://lex.uz//docs/-111460>

